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The Effects of Self-Efficacy and Self-Regulated Learning to Academic Achievement

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was conducted to determine the effect between self-efficacy and self-regulated learning to academic achievement in students of class X SMKS 3 Taman Siswa Central Jakarta. This research was conducted for two months, that is from May to June 2018. The method used in this research is survey method. The population in this study were all students of SMKS 3 Taman Siswa Central Jakarta amounting to 136 students. With reference on the table Isaac and Michael the number of samples in this study as many as 95 respondents. The coefficient of determination t calculation on Self efficacy variables of 2.392 and t count on Self-Regulation in Learning variables of 2.276. Where t table of 1.986, it can be concluded self-efficacy variables and self-regulation in learning has a significant positive effect on academic's achievement. Because t count > t table. for Test F, found Fcount equal to 14,809 > Ftable equal to 3,10. This means there is a simultaneous influence between Self Efficacy and SelfRegulation variables in Academic Achievement because Fcount > Ftable. Multiple regression equation obtained result $\hat{Y} = 68,043 + 0,4128X_1 + 0,052X_2$. The coefficient value of determination R² is 0,244. This means self-efficacy variables (X₁) and Self-Regulated Learning (X₂) on Achievement Learning (Y) as much as 24,4%.

Keyword: Self-Efficacy, Self-Regulated, Learning, Academic, Achievement

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INTRODUCTION

High school level educational institutions are the final level of student status for students before they continue to a higher level, namely becoming a student in college or becoming an employee in a company. At this level, students learn to show their quality in order to get high achievement at school. High learning achievement can be achieved by following the process of good teaching and learning activities in the classroom. This activity aims to produce positive changes towards maturity, as far as various changes can be sought through efforts in the learning process.

Learning will produce changes in a person, to find out how far the changes that occur need to be assessed, as well as what happens to a student who follows a learning process at school, an assessment must always be made of his learning outcomes to determine the extent to which students have achieved their learning goals.

Learning achievement is the result achieved after students do learning at school. Learning achievement is obtained from the learning outcomes of each subject at school. Every school certainly expects its students to get good grades in each subject so that the school can compete with schools of the same level, because good learning achievement is a reflection that the school has succeeded in providing every knowledge to its students, and vice versa. SMKS 3 Taman Siswa is a vocational school in the field of business and management expertise which is located at Jalan Matraman Dalam II, Central Jakarta, with Accounting and Office Administration expertise programs. The school plays an active role in directing, educating, and fostering its students to gain knowledge and skills in their respective fields of expertise. Thus, the school expects students to get good learning achievements while at school in order to become Table 1.1 Percentage of odd grades of students at SMKS 3 Taman Siswa

Source: data processed by researchers

No.	Percentage Value	Number of students
1	28 %	38
2	46 %	62
3	26 %	35
Number of students		135

excellent and competent individuals in accordance with their respective fields of expertise.

There are many subjects taught at school, of course not all students can absorb all lessons while in class because the ability of each student to absorb material is different. So that it causes the learning achievement of each student in school to be different, from the achievement data that researchers take in the form of odd semester report cards in 2017/2018 it is found that there are still many students whose scores are still below the Minimum Completion Criteria (KKM) standard of 75 in each subject.

Based on the table above, students who exceeded the minimum completeness criteria (KKM) were 26%, the value coincided with the KKM was 28%, and the value that did not reach the KKM was 46%, which means that there are still many students who have not reached the KKM. Learning achievement is influenced by various factors, this can be seen from the different learning achievement scores of students from one another. Schools as formal educational institutions have certainly carried out learning in their schools well, the aim is to improve the learning achievement of their students. However, the achievement of each student's efforts tends to be different from one another due to various factors.

Many factors influence low student achievement, one of which is low student interest in learning. Interest in learning in learning activities is a driving force for these students to remain enthusiastic about participating in learning activities in the classroom. In classroom learning, students who have low interest in learning tend to feel bored and bored when in class. From the results of interviews with teachers, there are still many students who have low interest in learning, such as the number of students who do not concentrate on listening to the material explained by the teacher, there are still many students who leave the class when the lesson is in progress, skip class, and come to school late. This will certainly have an impact on low learning achievement at school.

The second factor is the lack of student learning readiness at school which is still low. This low learning readiness can be seen from the response or reciprocity of a student to a teacher when giving answers to a teacher's questions during a lesson. Another thing can also be seen from the completeness and learning resources brought by students in learning activities. Based on interviews with teachers, it was found that there were still students who did not bring textbooks or notebooks in learning activities with the excuse of forgetting or something else.

This indicates that students at SMKS 3 Taman Siswa are not ready to take part in the learning process in class. The learning process will pass without any maximum results from students to learn. As a result, students will have difficulty in following the next lesson and find it difficult to respond to the teacher in the classroom learning process from the lessons that have been obtained. This low learning readiness will certainly have an impact on student learning achievement which is decreasing.

The third factor that affects low learning achievement is low self-regulation in learning. Self-regulation in learning means the ability to organize and plan learning activities. This can be seen from the fact that there are still many students who only start studying when the test or exam time is about to begin, do not have complete lesson notes, and only do homework assignments at school by copying friends' answers (cheating). Based on the results of interviews with teachers at SMKS 3 Taman Siswa, it is found that there are still students who are not ready when the exam will take place, this is indicated by the number of students who cheat when the exam is taking place.

Another behavior related to low regulation in student learning is not knowing if asked about previous material by the teacher because they did not study the previous material which causes students to have difficulty continuing the next material. If this continues, it will have an impact on students' low learning achievement at school. The fourth factor is low self-efficacy. Self-efficacy is the ability to believe in oneself to complete certain tasks. Efficacy can influence a person's mindset or motivation to act. When someone has high self-efficacy, of course their motivation to learn at school will be high and this will have an impact on good learning achievement at school. However, when students have low self-efficacy, it will

make students not maximize the learning process in class which will have an impact on low learning achievement at school.

Based on researcher interviews with teachers at SMKS 3 Taman Siswa, this low self-efficacy factor is still found in some students at school, such as when entering subject matter that students do not like, students will tend not to do the assignments given because they already judge that they are unable to master the material that has previously been given. Or when the test will take place, students will ask the teacher in advance when the corrective test will be held, even though they have not worked on the test questions.

Another symptom associated with low student self-efficacy is the behavior of being shy to appear in front of the class when the teacher tells them to come forward to re-explain the material that has been explained or for other things. Students tend to be silent in class, because they think there are still many who deserve to come forward than themselves. Not asking if there is material that has not been understood when the teacher invites students to ask, not confident in doing the tasks given by the teacher, and a less competitive classroom atmosphere.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Learning Achievement

Hawadi (Siti Suminarti, 2013): Learning achievement is "the learning process experienced by students and results in changes in knowledge, understanding, application, analysis power, synthesis, and evaluation.

Winkel (Hamdani, 2011): Learning achievement is evidence of the success that has been achieved by a person, thus learning achievement is the maximum result that a person achieves after carrying out learning efforts.

Arif Gunarso (Hamdani, 2011): Learning achievement is the maximum effort achieved by a person after carrying out efforts in learning.

Qohar (Hamdani, 2011): Learning achievement is the result that has been created, the result of work, the result of pleasing the heart obtained by tenacity.

Mardjohan (Siti Suminarti, 2013): Academic achievement is a key indicator that shows a student's mastery of the knowledge material taught at school.

Sumadi Suryabrata (Saefullah, 2012): factors and learning achievements can be classified into two parts, namely: internal factors: factors that come from within students that can affect learning achievement external factors: factors from outside themselves that affect student learning achievement.

Kompri (Kompri, 2015): Learning achievement is the result of learning that is obtained, and is evident in each student in the form of additional knowledge, the emergence of new experiences, and changes in behavior. The learning process always results in learning outcomes being achieved. From here a picture can be taken of the success of learning in the form of determining the report card.

Self-efficacy

Bandura (Charli, 2015): Self-efficacy is an individual's belief in his or her ability to perform a task, achieve goals, and overcome problems or obstacles.

Robbins (Robbins, 2012): Self efficacy refers to an individual's belief that he or she is capable of performing a task.

Santrock, (Santrock 2009): Self-Efficacy is the belief that I can.

Maddux (Carole, 2008): Self-efficacy as what I believe I can do with my skills under certain conditions.

BarondanByrn, (Baron 2004): Self-efficacy is an individual's assessment of their ability or competence to perform a task, achieve a goal, and produce something.

Jeanne Ellis (Jeanne, 2011): Self efficacy is a person's self-constructed judgment about his or her ability to execute certain behaviors or reach certain goals.

Agoes Dariyo (Agoes, 2011): Self Efficacy is an individual's belief characterized by the confidence to do something well and successfully.

Kreitner and Kinicki (Kreitner, 2011): Self efficacy is a person's level of belief or confidence in one's own strength (self-confidence) in doing and carrying out certain tasks or jobs that result in success or success.

Mukhid (Mukhid, 2009): Self efficacy is a self-assessment belief regarding one's competence to succeed in tasks.

Bandura (Ghufron, 2016): Efficacy consists of 3 dimensions, namely: Magnitude: The level of difficulty of the task Strength: The level of strength or confidence in one's abilities. Generality: The extent of the behavioral field based on a specific situation.

Alex (Alex, 2013): Self-efficacy has three dimensions, namely: Magnitude: Refers to the interest in something that individuals believe they can overcome. Strength: Strength includes individual confidence in carrying out work at a specific level of difficulty. Generality: Generality refers to the extent to which expectations are common to all situations.

Bandura (Lunenbunrg, 2011): Self-efficacy has three dimensions: magnitude, the level of task difficulty a person believes she can attain; strength, the conviction regarding magnitude as strong or weak; and generality, the degree to which the expectation is generalized across situations.

Self-Regulation in Learning

Bandura (Siti Suminarti, 2013): Self-Regulated Learning as a state where the individual who learns as a controller of his own learning activities, monitors motivation and academic goals, manages human and material resources, and becomes a behavior in the process of decision making and executing in the learning process.

Pintrich and Zusho (David, 2006): Self-Regulated Learning as an active process that is constructive in setting learning goals and monitoring, regulating, controlling cognition, and behavior, which is supported by goals and the surrounding environment.

Bandura (Zimmerman, 2004): Individuals who have the ability to apply Self-Regulated Learning direct the learning process, and can plan their learning goals by applying strategies that are appropriate for them. appropriate to achieve their goals.

Schraw (Linda, 2013): There are 3 stages in Self-Regulated Learning: Planning, this stage is carried out before starting student learning activities, including determining learning targets, how to motivate themselves, setting time in completing tasks, choosing strategies to be used and detecting obstacles that may occur in carrying out tasks. Monitoring, this stage is carried out during the learning process to find out whether the use of strategies in carrying out tasks has gone according to plan, evaluation, this stage is carried out after the learning process ends where students assess the results of achieving their learning objectives that have been set as well as assessing how well students master the material that has been taught.

Ertner and Newby (Henk, 2000): Self-Regulated Learning shows that learners play an active role in planning, monitoring, and evaluating their learning process.

Zusho and Edwards (Heater Fry, 2015): the cycle in self-regulated learning is: Forethought Phase, is the stage of student perception and planning, namely by analyzing tasks, and setting strategic goals in learning. Performance Phase, is the stage of self-control and observation. The Self-Reflection Phase is when the learner adjusts goals, processes, and strategies to their performance.

Zimmerman (Andrew, 2005): there are three phases in the Self-Regulated Learning cycle, namely:

1. Forethouhgt phase: is the thinking phase,
2. Performance phases: is the performance phase
3. Self-Reflection Phases: is the reflection phase.

Zimmerman and Schunk (Kusaeri, 2016): Self-regulation have three aspects that are applied to learning, namely: Metacognition, students who have self-regulation can plan, organize, instruct, monitor and evaluate themselves in the learning process. Motivation, students who learn will feel themselves competent / capable, have high self-efficacy and are able to create behavior to meet a goal or several desired goals. Behavior, students who learn are able to select, arrange, and organize themselves to be more optimal in learning through habits and interactions carried out

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The method used in this study is a survey method through simple observations and interviews with a correlation approach and using primary data for the independent variables of self-efficacy (X1) and self-regulation in learning (X2) and secondary data for the dependent variable of learning achievement (Variable Y). the affordable population in this study were all class X SMKS 3 Taman Siswa students totaling 135 students.

To determine the effect of self-efficacy (X1) and self-regulation in learning (X2) on learning achievement (Y), the constellation of influence between variables XI and X2 on Y can be described as follows:

Figure III.1

Constellation of Relationships Between Variables

Description:

X1: Self-efficacy

X2: Self-Regulation in Learning

Y: Learning Achievement

→: Direction of influence

RESEARCH RESULT

The results of the analysis requirements test show that the data is normally distributed, the regression model does not occur multicollinearity and there is no heteroscedasticity problem.

Based on the research conducted, the regression equation of self-efficacy and self-regulation in learning-on-learning achievement is $Y = 68.043 + 0.128X1 + 0.052X2$. In this regression equation, it is known that the constant value (a) is 68.043. This can be interpreted if self-efficacy (X) and self-regulation in learning (X2) the value is 0, then work productivity (Y) has a value of 68.043.

Based on the hypothesis testing carried out, the results of the F test can be seen that the Fcount value is $14.809 > F_{table} 3.10$, so it can mean that self-efficacy and self-regulation in learning together have an effect on learning achievement. Then in the calculation of the t test obtained tcount self-efficacy of 2.392. Based on these results, ttable is 1.986. From these data it can be seen that $t (2.392) > t_{table} (1.986)$. So, it can be concluded that the self-efficacy variable has a significant influence on learning achievement. While the t of self-regulation in learning is $2.276 > t_{table} (1.986)$,

Based on the results of multiple regression research, the coefficient of determination obtained by looking at R² is 0.244. It can be interpreted that the ability of the variables of self-efficacy and self-regulation in learning to explain learning achievement simultaneously is 24.4%. While the remaining 75.6% is influenced by other factors.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion regarding the influence of self-efficacy and self-regulation in learning-on-learning achievement in class X students at SMKS 3 Taman Siswa Central Jakarta, the following conclusions can be drawn:

There is an influence between self-efficacy and learning achievement of 2.39 or 2.39%. The higher the student's self-efficacy, the higher the learning achievement.

There is an influence between self-regulation in learning and learning achievement of 2.27 or 2.27%. The higher the self-regulation in learning students, the higher the learning achievement they get at school.

There is an influence between self-efficacy and self-regulation in learning-on-learning achievement of 0.244 or 24.4%.

RECOGNITION

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